

SOME CONSIDERATIONS ON THE CONCEPT OF LIQUID MODERNITY FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF THE ORTHODOX THEOLOGY

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ABSTRACT: Some Considerations on the Concept of Liquid Modernity from the Perspective of the Orthodox Theology.

In this study we propose to analyze the concept of liquid Church, which is provisionally defined as the deinstitutionalized Christian religion that still presents some resemblance to the Christian Church as an expression of communion with Christ. Resulting from the distinction between early or solid modernity and late or liquid modernity, in our opinion, this concept offers the Orthodox missionary possibilities for interpreting and evaluating the forms of religious praxis that we encounter outside the institutionalized church as manifestations of the existence of the church. Within these aspects, the question that imposes itself to be resolved lies in the occurrence with which the liquid church proposes itself as a Christian ecclesiological space, as well as the specification of its main characteristics that recommend it as a church and even more so as a church that fulfills the commandments of Christ.

As such, we propose to create a syntagm of liquid church as a variation of Zygmunt Bauman's concept of liquid modernity in the context of the missionary work that the Church of Christ has to carry out in the dynamics of the transition from late modernity to postmodernity where, according to the directions generated by the ecumenical movement, Churches seek to develop the most appropriate missionary activities, such as that relating to understanding the dimensions of suffering, in order to preserve the world in its natural ecclesiological space.

Keywords: mission, church, liquid modernity, destructuring, community

In this brief study we will refer to the concept of liquid church, which can provisionally be defined as the deinstitutionalized Christian religion that still presents some resemblance to the Church as we know it as an expres-

sion of communion with Christ. Resulting from the distinction between early or solid modernity and late or liquid modernity, this concept offers possibilities for interpreting and evaluating the forms of religious praxis that we encounter outside the institutionalized church as manifestations of church existence. In this context, it must be emphasized that, in general, religious praxis that takes place outside the regime of religious institutions is often interpreted at the individual level. Within these aspects, the question that proposes itself to be resolved lies in the occurrence with which the liquid church proposes itself as a Christian ecclesiological space, as well as the specification of its main characteristics that recommend it as a church and even more so as a church that fulfills the commandments of Christ. Although those who speak of the liquid church consider it to be the true church because it is, as they consider, marked by the authentic communication of the Word and the Holy Sacraments, they do not explain, for example, how the Holy Sacraments are fulfilled¹.

Moreover, it is a contradictory reality, because the same author vehemently criticizes the Sunday liturgical practice, while not offering an alternative to this church ordinance that gives the Church its sacramental character. This aspect highlights the fact that the liquid church is more of an evangelical type than a Church defined by its sacramental works instituted by Christ.

In this study we propose an evaluation of the syntagm liquid church as a variation of Zygmunt Bauman's concept of liquid modernity in the context of the missionary work that the Church of Christ has to carry out in the dynamics of the transition from late modernity to postmodernity where, according to the directions generated by the ecumenical movement, the Churches seek to develop the most appropriate missionary activities, such as the one related to understanding the dimensions of suffering, in order to keep the world in its natural ecclesiological space.

Operating principles of the liquid Church

In this context, the antinomy between the liquid church and the solid church becomes evident. The solid church is a living, concrete reality, the

1 P. Ward, *Liquid Church*, Hendrickson/Pater Noster, Peabody/Carlisle, 2002, pp. 67-68.

result of a process whose idea has materialized over time, based on Holy Scripture, Holy Tradition, the dogmatic sources of the seven Ecumenical Councils and the teachings of the Holy Fathers. A Church that has taken the form of relationships between concrete realities and that offers man the possibility of attaining deification. It is the result of a divine and human work whose dynamics have made the movement of the world a reality with a static character: a historical certainty. The only church that, through its theology, has gone through a solid and real process of reification.

The liquid church, unlike the solid church, has a different approach to the ecclesiological reality. For example, although the liquid church is all about the people of the church, those who preach this vision believe that the time has come to stop considering the church as an institution, because by sacralizing an institution, we are actually sacralizing the time we live in, not the person. As such, "the emergent church is rediscovering a forgotten Gospel - the idea that its emphasis is not so much on personal salvation from sin, but on the fact that we have an invitation from God to participate with Him in the act of redeeming the world."²

This way, the participation in church services, the involvement in philanthropic activities, for the proper functioning and organization of the parish, for example, are seen as expressions of a behavior and a mentality specific to the way modern institution's function. Facts that, in their opinion, more or less, impose the need for a deinstitutionalization of the Christian faith. The solutions they propose are varied; thus, it is taken into consideration promoting new ways of being a church, similar to the ways of organization that already exist in contemporary culture, such as: groups of Christians who support each other in local initiatives by reading the scriptural text or other uplifting texts, by performing prayers of praise to God, other than those performed in the liturgical church space, organizing events such as festivals where people sing, organizing contests and meetings on various faith-related topics, but also an intense preaching of the word of Christ in both old and new media. Those who preach the reality of the liquid church talk about the need to understand that only such free activities are those that actually make up what we denominate as a church.

Therefore, the involvement and the belonging to the solid church ministry are no longer enough to build bridges that lead to the realization

2 C. Ghioancă, *op. cit.*, p. 51.

of a “true” church. In its essence, the church is not only the place where Christ is communicated to those present and in which divine Grace works. Only through a movement in continuous adaptation and movement, always dynamic like a liquid, Church can be, and often is, a church. This type of conceptualization carries interesting implications in the development of this model of ecclesial praxis. And this is because, for example, the liquid church that does not result from the vision of a project, cannot be evaluated or controlled by the leaders or organizations that administer it. However, in order to organize itself and be functional, the liquid church considers that the use of already existing communication networks, which exist as a result of the connection of countless series of nodes, whether individuals, organizations, communication systems or political structures, are sufficient to offer it to the world as a viable alternative³.

In this respect, those who support the idea of a liquid church believe that there are three indicators that allow these different networks to “work for us”⁴. The first of them refers to the expansion of opportunities that facilitate different ways of encounters in the name of Christ. The second focuses on the development of products that stimulate the connection between people. And the third has as objective the organization and invitation of people to events that propose for debate various interesting topics related to spending free time or other cultural and social topics, such as the awareness of the major role that the citizen has in political life or discussions about the power of the freely expressed vote. Above all, there is a supreme indication that must manifest itself within all these activities and events whose ultimate objective is the conviction of the participants that in everything they do they fulfill the will of God because God is already with them. This does not mean that the church “happens” wherever religious communication takes place. Because the liquid church must give priority to “special grace”⁵ and remain permanently focused on fulfilling the work of the divine Spirit that is manifested in the world for its salvation. Although it may be provocative, this world of the liquid church seems to promise a postmodernity devoid of any theological value and especially of any human principles and values.

3 P. Ward, *op. cit.*, pp. 41-42.

4 *Ibidem*, p. 98.

5 *Ibidem*, p. 85.

The idea of developing products that generate relationships between human beings appears in this context as one of the most provocative suggestions. It is also the cause that gave rise to the concept of commodification⁶ which, in this case, refers to the sale of religious products using modern marketing techniques, an aspect that offers us the possibility of formulating an alternative definition of the liquid church, which here is perceived as a network of communication and consumption proposed as a recipe for the salvation in Christ.

Unlike the missionary work of the Church, which has at its center the preaching of Christ to the “ends of the world” (Romans 10:18), the supporters of the liquid church do not want to vitalize or strengthen their religious congregations. The forms of the liquid church are contained in the informal, ephemeral and commercial reality, where, whether or not they are loosely connected to one or more religious institutions, they cannot in any way, in their opinion, be tainted and altered. Their value resides in their presence, regardless of whether or not they have effects on the solid church; this indifference actually hides the relationship of the liquid church with the solid church. First of all, because Christian believers are, in turn, both participants in the events organized by the liquid churches and buyers of religious products or are even pilgrims or religious tourists within the events organized by these congregations. What alters the sense of belonging is that existing, institutionalized religion can become the expression of a whole process of divine and human events. In this respect, almost imperceptibly, the innovative initiatives of the liquid church very subtly transform into standard procedure and common practice even for solid churches.

Being Church in the conditions of liquid modernity

The almost gloomy image of liquid modernity that Zygmunt Bauman proposes seems difficult to associate with the propaganda that promotes the liquid church. Continuing to follow the same line already drawn by theorists such as Ulrich Beck, Manuel Castells, Michel Foucault and Pierre Bourdieu, Z. Bauman sketches a world in which the boundaries between

6 „Commodification is associated with a loss of human forces and development. The social powers of self-development are explained within a framework of commodification and labor”. Sorin Cace, *Statul bunăstării. Evoluții și tendințe*, Editura Expert, București, 2004, p. 152.

classes or the social status of people are cancelled. For these reasons, man has so many options that identity is no longer prescribed to him, but must be constructed; being only at this stage truly free, man might be inclined to react. Z. Bauman draws attention, however, that it is too easy to believe in the ideology of the free market, because it is marked by neoliberalism and hedonism, ideologies that in fact do not offer us any kind of freedom. If in solid modernity man was determined by the role that the production process gave him, in liquid modernity, man is determined by the role he has in the consumer society. The market, therefore, has become more powerful today than the state, the church, or the family once were. Postmodern man is always tempted to buy those products that offer him the illusory state of an "authentic" identity; as such, the personal task of constructing his own identity has become the greatest personal burden.

Moreover, through the open communication offered by social networks and communication platforms or global communication networks, man has acquired the ability to fulfill multiple social roles; being a single soul with multiple faces has profoundly altered his identity. However, there is no escape from the reflexive project of the self⁷, because man cannot live without choosing. Through the choices he makes, he defines himself; he always has to choose: how to dress, what to do, what to eat or what to believe in. The articulation of those ways of being in the world is also the result of a personal choice, even where he lives according to customs and traditions. To live means to be autonomous while being flexible, mobile and adaptable to working from home or in the office, full-time or part-time. To be everywhere at the same time, without belonging to one place, which is why an exasperated longing for home grows in every man. This is a description of a common self that is often very volatile and deceptive because it carries the traits of a dominant ideology, of those who are successful in life, of those who have valued the condition of human individuality, while most people have not acquired the capacity to manifest themselves authentically, individually, freely; and, because they do not have the capacity to practice individuality *de facto*⁸, they do not have much choice, which is why they must accept life as it comes. They are *de jure* individuals whose identity

7 A. Giddens, *Modernity and Self-Identity: Self and Society in the Late Modern Age*, Polity Press, Cambridge, 1991, pp. 70-109.

8 Zygmunt Bauman, *Community: Seeking Safety in an Insecure World*, Polity Press, Cambridge, 2001, p. 58.

defines them as autonomous individuals, but, in fact, they are completely dependent on structures that they cannot influence.

Z. Bauman presents here the image of a stationary community in which each person knows his place and people know each other so well that they have common interests that never separate. It is a utopia of the community offered as an alternative to the dystopia that liquid modernity proposes to the world today in which community, in a real way, is no longer possible. However, today there are beautiful communities, true closed paradises, created by the rich, perceived as unsafe precisely because of their perfection, just as there are ghettos of the poor, of the marginalized, who in the neighborhood where they live together do not find themselves in the community, do not belong to the place. Fraternity is missing because stigma and humiliation do not transform those marginalized and those in suffering into brothers⁹.

What Z. Bauman describes is a reaffirmation of the classical ideals of social justice transposed into the context of modernity: the redistribution of the means by which each person participates in the realization of the social, private and collective life, in order to defend human dignity by creating fair conditions of equal opportunities. It is about the ontological security of the human person by promoting social solidarity; it is about "the mixture of distributive justice and the politics of recognition"¹⁰.

For Z. Bauman, the role of the religious institutions, in this concern regarding human solidarity and the salvation of human identity, is not a prolific one for man, as he also understands the family, social class or neighborhood; for him, these institutions are both alive and dead¹¹ in the current world, because they have lost their authority. Families fall apart, differences between social classes disappear, neighborhoods disintegrate and identities can be changed. On the other hand, this de-structuring of the world contains within itself the new meaning of these institutions. The current world offers the possibility and the ability to choose, a fact that erases the importance of the institution that no longer attributes the identity of something or someone, as in a previous phase of modernization, but is now chosen. In this way, the relationship with institutions is individualized.

9 *Ibidem*, p. 121.

10 *Ibidem*, p. 78.

11 Z. Bauman, *Liquid Modernity*, Polity Press, Cambridge, 2000, p. 6.

In this case, Church, in its capacity as an institution - even if not one of the modern ones - is viewed from the same perspectives. Although the institution exists, it has lost its capacity as a binder, as a creator of a symbol and structure that serves the idea of a nation-state, a traditional region or even a social network in a virtual environment. As such, sacred space is something private, personal in which the church is the expression of an individual choice.

Z. Bauman's vision of the church in liquid modernity describes a community that shares the same values and beliefs and practices the same religious traditions. For him, church is similar to the ethnic community, in which people of different origins and beliefs are in a relationship of interdependence: it is the church that offers the experience of belonging. But this type of community is not a living and real one, because the people in such a church are not the people with whom one works, with whom one lives, with whom one exists. It is the "refuge church" that presents itself as a mutation of the solid church.

At the same time, in liquid modernity, Church is an aesthetic, "instantaneous" community, a fact reflected by the spontaneous way in which participants gather at religious events which, through the spectacular way in which they are presented to them, offer those present the feeling of belonging to something that transcends the world and man. For a moment, this type of community offers participants a sense of community that does not require any type of commitment or long-term obligations¹²; a mix of identity and freedom. However, in this case we are no longer talking about community, because, according to Z. Bauman, the community is not made up of people only for a certain period of time. And if we accept such temporary communities, then these are "locker room" and "carnival" communities, lacking the authenticity that usually defines the community: comprehensive and sustainable. Therefore, the current church suffers from symptoms caused by the disorder of liquid modernity¹³. Therefore, from the perspective of emerging churches, the church carries the image of a "heritage place" and a "nostalgic community", unlike the modern liquid church.¹⁴

A real, human community, made up of people, can be and must be a community interweaved from sharing and mutual assumption; a com-

12 Z. Bauman, *Community: Seeking Safety*, pp. 69-70.

13 Idem, *Liquid Modernity*, pp. 199-201.

14 P. Ward, *op. cit.*, pp. 22-25.

munity in which all those who are part of it are responsible and concerned with respecting equitably the right to be human as well as, equally, the ability to act on the basis of this right.¹⁵ Here we can note some visible similarities between Z. Bauman's vision of man and the world and the teaching of Christian theology, especially with regard to the missionary work of the Church.

Church's Mission in Liquid Modernity

The liquid state of the current world, as presented by Z. Bauman, sheds light on the tense relationship between postmodernity and today's churches and, at the same time, highlights the role that churches should play in this context. For Z. Bauman, churches should respond to liquid modernity by creating those social levers that lead to the creation of a just society. For this reason, in his vision, liquid modernity must be viewed by churches with critical eyes. However, through this approach, Z. Bauman shows that, viewed as a liquid structure, the current world offers churches new means of exploring man's interest in religion, because the association of the church's desire for ontological security and the realization of human solidarity by man, as classical functions of religion, can give rise to appropriate missionary means that further strengthen the religious message. The sociological analysis accomplished by Z. Bauman also carries the character of an invitation addressed to Christian theology to reconsider the way in which it articulates Its Christian message to the cultures of the postmodern world by favoring pleas dedicated to the development of human communities. This is what missionary theology has developed using the concept of interculturalization, assumed especially from anthropology, sociology and psychology, but also encountered in other fields of humanistic research.¹⁶

In fulfilling this, the Orthodox missionary can emphasize that the liquid church is not a reality resulting from liquid modernity, but rather a way of perceiving liquid modernity. In this perspective, rigorously looked upon, the relationship between emerging, liquid churches and man - which

15 Z. Bauman, *Community: Seeking Safety*, pp. 149-150.

16 Pierre Dasen, „Fundamentele științifice ale unei pedagogii interculturale”, în Pierre Dasen, Chrsthiane Perregaux, Micheline Rey, *Educație interculturală. Experiențe, politici, strategii*, Traducere Adriana Mornanu, Ana Maria Biliuc, Anda Sandovici, Editura Polirom, Iași, 1999, (21-54), p. 32.

today appears to be flourishing in contrast to the way of remaining connected to solid churches - reveals to the Orthodox missionary the level of spirituality and the intensity with which it manifests itself in today's world. In this respect, this connection refers to the way in which the causes that generate these movements on the quick sands of the human spirit are interpreted and the way in which it helps the Orthodox missionary in formulating a theological assessment of liquid modernity. The argument underlying this approach arises from the undeniable fact that the human spirit is alive. Its spiritual desire to be part of the symphony of the sacred is rooted here. The churches must deal with it.

If liquid churches say: "Look, society is liquid! The church should be the same!"; Z. Bauman only draws attention and says: "Attention! Liquid modernity!" Moreover, in our opinion, Z. Bauman does nothing more than highlight the difference between the way we approach the concept of liquid church and the way we should position ourselves and react in the conditions of liquid modernity. This differentiation reveals his concern to identify the most appropriate means by which the Christian faith not only remains active, but also becomes more attractive to people living in today's consumer society, which shows that missionary work has, to an extent that we must take into account, also an economic character.

Returning to the ideology of liquid churches, their representatives argue that it is unfair for church to define itself as the bearer of Christian traditions, because Christ is universal and the Christian faith is a personal expression external to society. Therefore, the challenge addressed to Christian believers is to build bridges; to this end, it is necessary to organize "liquid" meetings, products and events that increase the attractiveness of liquid churches. The basic idea is that the church should find ways to integrate itself better and more into the life of contemporary society in order to be available to all those who seek salvation. The subliminal message is that people should be given as many opportunities as possible to enter the structure of churches, which is a good idea for the church, but it is not a clear enough idea for people, because formulated and applied in this way, it does not shed light on why it is so good for people to be in the church. It is an approach that, while affirming the presence of God in His creation, establishes such a great distance between the church and society that it presents the church not as a certain place of deification, but more as a safe shelter.

The liquid approach challenges the solid church to build new missionary arguments to explain its mission in this world, where the liquid church focuses not on the survival of the idea of the church in its current structure, but on the idea of the church itself. Z. Bauman proposes an original approach; starting from the experience of insecurity, of increasingly oppressive social inequality, of the achievement of community and stability, he challenges churches to reformulate their missionary work. Therefore, in our opinion, the critical analysis of contemporary society that Z. Bauman carries out can constitute a useful theoretical source from which to carry out a hermeneutic reconstruction at least of the political and social missionary work of the solid churches¹⁷.

Conclusions

From this analysis we draw the conclusion that it is often easier to criticize than to realize an alternative. The incarnation of the Son of God, His death and resurrection, reveal God's love for the world he created. Christ's example of loving the world through sacrifice, through suffering, constitutes the most beautiful invitation addressed by God to love one another. The Kingdom of God as an eternal kingdom that the Holy Apostles speak about is an exhortation addressed to believers to assume and get involved, as if the Kingdom were already here, among us; a fact that, sometimes, we manage to achieve even in the challenging context of liquid modernity in which the Church of Christ manages to fulfill its missionary work to the extent that it remains firm in fulfilling justice, truth and especially deification.

A careful and positive reading of Z. Bauman's analysis gives rise to prolific perspectives for the missionary work of the Church. At the same time, it reveals the fact that missionary theology serves the Church by offering solutions to fulfill its mission even in the context of the concept of liquid modernity by creating articulated responses to the work that Christ gave to the Church. The disintegration and reintegration of liquid modernity in the Church are stages through which faith and human reason meet with the aim of introducing man into the saving universe of the Liturgy, into the communion that springs mutual appreciation and sacrifice between believers who see in the face of their companions the risen Christ.

17 F. Schüssler Fiorenza, *Foundational Theology. Jesus and the Church*, Crossroad, New York, 1984, pp. 164-223.

In this context, the concept of the liquid church must be considered to be sensitizing, because through it, Church can draw attention to those forms of religion expressed as networks of festivals, spiritual events or virtual communities, but also to those collective meetings and activities organized outside the religious area within the cultural, economic, medical or educational spheres. The notion of the liquid church is an idea that stimulates, exacerbates and thus alters missionary concepts such as: contextualization, interculturalization, identity, freedom, reality or the idea of leadership¹⁸, which shows that the main challenge that liquid churches launch to the current world consists in resizing the relationship between Church and culture.¹⁹

Another way of exacerbating the current reality by liquid churches is so subtle that solid churches practice it without feeling the danger that threatens them. In this regard, we can exemplify by mentioning the creation of pseudo-religious networks that are based on church initiatives in a secular environment, such as, for example, a hospital: a place of healing resulting from secular initiatives through which the work of Christ is communicated; or, in the cultural field, a theater institution where a drama that evokes religious experience can be presented. A museum that exhibits religious icons or a performance of sacred music organized in a concert hall where the public is invited to participate not in order to listen to the religious message, but to enjoy the presence of celebrities²⁰.

Therefore, the concept of the liquid church challenges theology to answer what it means, what it is, what is the nature of the relationship between theology and structure, themes that go deep into the Christian faith teaching concerning the relationship between the Persons of the Holy Trinity, for example; or the articulation of the soteriological teaching of the Church in a world whose structures are fluid. And, if we finally understand

18 N.T. Ammerman et al., *Congregation and Community*, Rutgers University Press, New Brunswick, NJ, 1997, pp. 36-62.

19 Ioan-Gheorghe Rotaru, "Aspects of the Relationship between Church and State", *Jurnalul Libertății de Conștiință (Journal for Freedom of Conscience)*, vol. 10 (2022), nr. 2, pp. 585-595.

20 P. Post, "Ritual-liturgical Movements. A Panoramic View on Ritual Repertoires in Dutch Catholicism after 1950/1960", in E. Sengers (ed.), *The Dutch and Their Gods. Secularization and Transformation of Religion in the Netherlands since 1950*, Verloren, Hilversum, 2005, (75-100), pp. 85-87.

that “the liquid church is not a program”²¹, only then do we understand how important it is to identify the dynamics behind liquid churches.

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21 Kees de Groot, *op. cit.*, p. 189.

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